

Impact of fiber aspect ratio on the mechanical performance of short fiber composites

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- › **Background & Motivation**
- › **Objectives**
- › **Experimental Approach**
- › **Results & Discussions**
- › **Conclusions**

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- › Conventional processing flow chart of composite parts

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- › Fibers recycling from composite scrap or end of life parts

- › Fiber length reduction (Aspect ratio (ξ))
 - › Fiber strength
 - › Interface quality
 - › Alignment & orientation
 - › Volume fraction
- Recycling approach
- Re-processing approach

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› Interface quality Recycling approach

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Tailored universal Feedstock for Forming (TuFF) Process

- Water based fiber deposition process
- Highly aligned short fiber preforms
- Performance similar to continuous composites

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- › Mechanical performance as a function of fiber ξ (length / diameter)
- › Investigating the processing quality
- › Comparison of experimental data with analytical models

Wang, Qiushi & Jones, Joydan & Lu, Na & Johnson, Ralph & Ning, Haibin & Pillay, Selvum. (2017). Development and characterization of high-performance kenaf fiber-HDPE composites. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*. 37. 073168441773912. 10.1177/0731684417739127.

- › Previous work on individual fiber lengths with increasing ξ
- › Consistent stiffness irrespective of fiber ξ
- › Increasing strength with increased ξ
- › Similar to continuous at $\sim 600 \xi$
- › Mixed ξ ???

Balaga, U.K., et. al. (2024). Influence of fiber aspect ratio on the mechanical performance of highly aligned short fiber composites. ASC Conference, San Diego.

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Preform processing

ID	ξ
P1 (3.25mm)	250
P2 (7.15mm)	550
P12 (mixed)	mix

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- Uniform distribution in TuFF composite (minimal voids or porosity in all cases) * ξ – Aspect ratio

- › TuFF baseline
 - Tight orientation
 - Higher FVF
- › TuFF P1, P2 & P12
 - Broader spread
 - As fiber ξ reduces, orientation reduces
 - More than 60% fibers within $\pm 15^\circ$

› Modulus

- Independent of Aspect Ratio
- Continuous composite data from technical data sheet

› Strength

- Increases with increasing ξ
- Mixed ξ strength between the two data points with higher inclination towards smaller ξ

- › Matrix dominated failure in the shorter fibers (low volume fraction, poor interface or inefficient load transfer)

- › Displacement – 0.05 inch/min
- › Failure Mode - LGM (ASTM 3039) (lateral gage middle)

■ Modelling: Property vs Aspect ratio

Model inputs	
Fiber volume fraction	0.25
Matrix volume fraction	0.75
Fiber strength	3500 MPa
Matrix strength	90 MPa
Fiber matrix interface strength	48 MPa
Diameter	13 μ m

l = Fiber length, l_c = Critical length

Model limitations in comparison with experimental results

- Stochastic fiber strengths
- Intensity of microcracking progressions
- Interface failures in short fiber composite
- Non – uniform fiber volume fractions and orientation

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Current:

- Experimental investigations of continuous and discontinuous composites.
- Alignment and packing efficiency analysis.
- Mechanical performance vs aspect ratio investigations with analytical models, experimental validations and interpretations.

Future Scope:

- Mechanical performance vs aspect ratio curve with fibers ranging lower and higher end of S-curve.
- Mixing of multiple fiber lengths at higher and lower end to investigate the mechanical behaviors.

Long term goals:

- Enabling closed loop recycling for sustainable manufacturing.
- High performance short fiber composites.

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